

ARDC Platforms

End of Project Report

This report is intended to be published and made available via the project's webpage on the ARDC website (certain sections can be redacted if requested). Please write this report for an audience who are not already familiar with this project.

Project Information

1. Project Details:

Project title: ARDC Environments to Accelerate Machine Learning Based Discovery

Lead organisation: Monash University

Other organisations involved in delivering the project: Queensland Cyber Infrastructure Foundation, University of Queensland

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Project start and end dates: 3 Feb. 2020 - 28 Feb. 2022

2. Background

The confluence of Big Data, Machine Learning (ML) techniques and parallel computing is making AI more powerful and more useful across a range of research areas. This is driving a strong and growing appetite across academic research groups for access to ML capacity, services, libraries, expertise and training.

Our community surveys and experience have shown that most novice ML practitioners begin their journey working on tutorials and simple use-cases on their local machines, possibly with a GPU available. They learn a popular language like Python and write code in easy, off the shelf environments like Jupyter notebooks (perhaps cloud-based, such as Google Colab) or as scripts within IDEs like Visual Studio Code or PyCharm. They might do so with a fixed, all-purpose set of libraries and modules, provided as a package, like those that are rolled into the Anaconda distribution.

As their expertise and research develops, however, their needs change substantially; they need more RAM, CPUs, GPUs, and GPU-RAM, and they require custom virtual environments (e.g. Conda, pip, containers). They turn to the High Performance Computing (HPC) infrastructure at their disposal. At Monash University, for example, researchers have access to MASSIVE and the Nectar Research Cloud.

At this juncture, there has historically been a chasm; a break-point in productivity and an intimidating learning curve. The overall aim of this project was to bridge this gap, achieved via three broad objectives: (i) to improve access and usability of compute infrastructure and tools for ML-based research; (ii) to provide educational opportunities to up-skill researchers in ML and HPC techniques, and (iii) build a supportive, vibrant, multidisciplinary, and national Community of Practice among ML researchers.

The ML environments developed under this project bring together ML tools, libraries, and access to data, across large GPU deployments nationally. They support core ML tools for preprocessing, annotating, training, and validation, and integrate with software development environments to provide a consolidated platform for ML-based research. The establishment of a national outreach and training program engages the researcher community and increases knowledge.

Researchers applying machine learning actively and broadly across disciplines is a new phenomenon. Therefore, we have collected significant information to ensure that this proposal is evidence based. The proposal is based on the outcomes from an international survey of research groups (referred to as the ML Requirements Survey) across Monash University, University of Queensland and University of Auckland undertaken under “ARDC Discovery Activity: Machine learning infrastructure deployed at scale: understanding requirements, demand, impact and international best practice”. The recommendations and report are available from this link: <http://bit.ly/MLResearchSurvey>.

This project focused on the key objectives below, which address the most pressing medium-term priorities identified in our researcher survey:

- **Bring together ML tools, libraries, and access to data, across large HPC/GPU deployments nationally.** The environments developed will support core ML tools for preprocessing, annotating, training, and validation, and provide a consolidated platform for ML-based research.
- **Support ML at scale through improved HPC efficiency and expertise** built on new benchmarking, parallelisation, and user documentation and resources. This will make more efficient use of available resources and improve the experience for researchers.
- **Develop and deliver a national outreach and training program to engage the researcher community and increase knowledge.** Training will be targeted around the most commonly used data preprocessing and ML tools & techniques (we found that Tensorflow, Keras, PyTorch, SciKit-learn and Caffe are used by 90% of the ML community surveyed).
- **Build Communities of Practice (CoP) around deep neural networks and applied ML domains such as health and HASS for exchange of knowledge and collaboration,** with a particular focus on gathering community requirements across major sites of activity.

Application areas underpinned by this project are very broad ranging from neuroscience, clinical science, molecular imaging, robotics, economics, design and architecture, and HASS.

Environments to Accelerate Machine Learning Based Discovery is a collaboration between Monash University, the Queensland Cyber Infrastructure Foundation, the University of Queensland, and affiliated institutions and national partners. The platform is developed and deployed at the eResearch facilities across Monash University (Monash eResearch/MASSIVE) and University of Queensland (Research Computing Centre), and across other partner sites, NCI and Pawsey. Access to this capability is available to project partners and nationally across all partner sites.

3. Achievement of project aims:

Outline the project aims and how they were achieved.

Work Packages 1 and 2 focused on delivering improved hardware, software, tools, documentation, and data access. Work Packages 3 and 4 focused on empowering people (researchers) to perform ML research and collaborate as a multi-disciplinary cohort of local and national communities. The project team was organised into two (overlapping) sub-teams to focus on these distinct challenges: The first consisted primarily of eResearch “DevOps” technicians and ML experts, while the second included experienced tutors, course developers, ML practitioners, and business analysts.

WP1: Accessible Tools, Libraries, Environments, and Data

This Work Package sought to make high performance computing and cloud environments hosted at Monash University, University of Queensland, and other project partner sites, more suitable for machine learning projects and more user-friendly. The aim was to allow ML researchers to more easily take the step from working on their local machines to working on powerful GPU-enabled HPC infrastructure, and ultimately achieve more in less time. This was achieved by:

1. Putting the necessary tools, data, and environments at their fingertips as much as possible.
2. Making the researcher’s user experience more similar to what they already know.
3. Reducing duplication of effort through centralised, well-tested solutions, repositories, and pathways.

These outcomes were achieved through Work Package items that included:

- Cataloguing of machine learning environments, tools, libraries, packages etc.
 - Informed by our community [surveys](#), interviews, and team workshops, we identified a set of key ML tools on which to focus our efforts. The greatest return on investment was deemed to come from improved resources for:
 - Python-based notebook environments (e.g. JupyterLab);
 - VS Code IDE for scripts in Python and other languages;
 - Tensorflow, PyTorch, Keras, Horovod;
 - Custom virtual environments through Conda, pip/virtualenv.
- GPU-enabled ML environments built on HPC/cloud infrastructure
 - *Strudel2*: We developed a simple browser-based interface for quick-connect, interactive access to customisable remote compute nodes (known as *Strudel2*; Figure 1)

Figure 1. A snapshot of the UI to select a GPU-enabled, remote JupyterLab instance

Strudel2 is a launchpad to access remote GPU and HPC compute resources, as well as a platform for interactivity through Linux-based (CVL) desktops, Python notebooks (JupyterLab), IDEs (VS Code), and standard command-line terminals. A simple interface allows the user to configure a request for an environment that meets their needs, including different types of GPU (from “small” to “large”), number of CPU cores, RAM allocation, and wall time. Under the hood, a resource request is issued via a SLURM scheduler and made ready for launch when available. In practice, the wait time is rarely more than a minute or two for most users at the time of writing. User documentation for Strudel2 is provided [here](#).

- Desktops
 - Strudel2 provides convenient access to the now well-established CVL desktops for interactive and visual requirements.
- JupyterLab
 - Users can launch a [JupyterLab](#) instance running on the custom remote compute resources requested through the Strudel2 interface, and hence are backed by powerful GPUs. In this sense, the environment is similar to Google’s Colab service, but more customisable, powerful (e.g. more RAM), and more secure because it is running on institutional hardware.
 - The environment has direct access to the same \$HOME directory and broader file-system available to users elsewhere in the institution's HPC system (e.g. whether accessed by ssh, SLURM jobs, VS Code, etc.). This allows a seamless transition between the user-friendly notebook environment and more traditional HPC approaches as required (e.g. when moving from a small to large project, or from interactive to non-interactive modes).
 - The notebook environment is launched with a default set of available Python tools and packages (e.g. Tensorflow, PyTorch, numpy etc.), much like the popular Anaconda distribution.

- [Custom environments](#) can be built using *miniconda* and *pip* to serve users with more specific needs.
 - *Visual Studio Code* (IDE)
 - We developed a simple workflow and automation routine which allows users to select their preferred flavour of compute node using the Strudel2 interface and then connect directly to that node through their local instance of VS Code via its in-built remote SSH server. This allows a fully-functional, local IDE to access the remote file system and execute code on the remote machine (e.g. on MASSIVE), including full use of debugging tools, selection of remote Python interpreters and environments, interactivity, and X11-forwarded graphics (e.g. for plotting).
 - This allows those already familiar with VS Code to continue with this powerful and intuitive interface even while developing and running code on an HPC- and GPU-enabled backend.
 - Once code development is complete, and interactivity is no longer required, compute-intensive tasks can be executed as a *tmux* (*smux*) session or as a SLURM *sbatch* script, all from within a VS Code terminal.
 - The connection is protected through SSH-key authentication.
 - The elapsed time between choosing a flavour of compute and a connected, working IDE is typically under a minute.
 - Under the hood, the SSH connection from VS Code triggers a launch script on the remote machine which finds the user's requested compute node and links it to the local VS Code instance automatically.
 - [Documentation](#) for accessing VS Code has been added to the M3 docs.
 - *MLeRP* (*Machine Learning eResearch Platform*)
 - The Machine Learning eResearch Platform provides national researchers with access to GPU accelerated JupyterLab sessions through a user-friendly interface, very similar to the JupyterLab offering mentioned above.
 - MLeRP differs from Strudel2 in a few key ways, including:
 - The platform is not restricted to users of one particular HPC, and is intended to serve the national research community;
 - The platform is not constrained by the diversity of users found on a typical HPC, opening it up to customisations informed by the machine learning community. This might be integration of specific tools and software (Tensorboard, Weights and Biases, the software installed, or the availability of core reference datasets), or changes to hardware configuration to best suit our users (changing the default resource allocations, configuring SLURM queues to maximise throughput for machine learning jobs.)
 - MLeRP is currently in an Alpha testing phase with 14 test users across 4 institutions (Monash University, University of Queensland, the CSIRO, and Griffith University). Access is currently granted on a user by user basis, with

plans to implement an approval process and automated account provisioning in future.

- Once users gain access to MLeRP, they login via AAF in a web browser at <https://mlerp.cloud.edu.au/>.
 - Resources are then requested via the Strudel interface - users simply select how long they require resources for, and press the “Launch” button.
 - In the background, a job is scheduled on a SLURM cluster of A100 GPUs hosted in the Nectar Research Cloud. We have sliced the A100 GPUs using Multi-Instance GPU technology and currently only offer A100 slices with 10G of vRAM. This offers enough GPU compute to get started training neural networks of building random forests, and can be adjusted as research needs grow.
 - Users will then be presented with a “Connect” button, which will open a GPU accelerated instance of JupyterLab in a new tab. This environment comes with common machine learning Python packages installed, such as Tensorflow. There are plans to replicate and extend the custom JupyterLab environment features present on MASSIVE, including buttons to remove environments that are no longer required.
- Improved support for custom Python environments (*conda / pip*)
 - We developed an installation [script](#) which installs *Miniconda* in a default configuration that reduces likelihood of common problems on HPC environments.
 - First, the script simplifies the installation for non-experts.
 - Second, it ensures that the default installation location of the software and packages is in the user’s scratch space and not in \$HOME. This reduces the likelihood of accidentally exhausting the relatively small \$HOME disk quota with environment packages (a common occurrence and productivity killer!).
 - Finally, it sets up the standard distribution Python environment for the Strudel2-based Jupyter/iPython notebooks.
 - Improved [documentation](#) covering the fundamentals of Python/Conda environments and how to ensure reproducibility and portability of environments and code execution (e.g. via export of an *environment.yml*).
 - ML Environments for training courses
 - The JupyterLab notebooks within Strudel2 were used as the platform for a training course at Monash (“*AI with Deep Learning (PyTorch)*”) as a proof of concept. We reserved sufficient compute resources for the class and found it to be a very smooth process, with no authentication issues or technical difficulties. This will be used for future courses.
 - Documentation and user experience
 - Documentation for our HPC systems has been improved with the ML community in mind, many examples of which are linked throughout this report. We have also included a new [section](#) specifically directed at ML users to provide a quick overview of key information.
 - Data collections

- ML users often rely on reference data sets for testing or benchmarking their models and algorithms. For example, the ImageNet database is used widely in the field of computer vision. A challenge for system administrators is that these reference data sets are often bulky, include a very large number of files, and are duplicated in the file system for every user who performs their own install. We identified an opportunity to offer a centralised, shared copy of these data collections to reduce waste and simplify access for ML users.
 - We pursued a thorough review of widely used data collections and selected a small number to host. An internal presentation outlining this process is [here](#). Factors that determined our choices included:
 - Data set size: can we afford to have multiple copies on the system?
 - Data set popularity: do we know of research groups using the data on the cluster?
 - Licencing and access: is it challenging to accommodate the data licencing requirements?
 - A description of the selected data collections is [here](#).
- In addition, many machine learning datasets consist of many small files, and operations on these datasets aren't performant on the parallel file systems which are typical of HPC environments. We created a 10TB NFS mount on MASSIVE to host some ML data collections to improve performance on these datasets.

WP2: Machine Learning at Scale

WP2 focused on improving the way machine learning is undertaken on HPC facilities to maximise productivity through benchmarking hardware performance, improved access to and use of parallelisation, and better documentation to communicate crucial information to users.

- We Identified suitable benchmarking tools and tested them on both MASSIVE (Monash) & Wiener (UQ) infrastructure. These tools evaluated performance for typical ML tasks (e.g. training and inference) for the different GPUs available to researchers. Outcomes include:
 - Selection of [ai-benchmark](#) as our tool of choice, after reviewing multiple alternatives including [MLPerf](#) and [Cosmoflow](#). We found other options were not well developed enough to execute on our infrastructure at the time of investigation, and chose ai-benchmark for its breadth of tests and ease of implementation.
 - Testing on hardware at both sites and reporting of results for [M3](#) and [Wiener](#) (Figures 2a and 2b)
 - Improved [documentation](#) on choosing a GPU, in part based on these results
 - A [repository](#) to allow users to repeat the tests we have performed and for sysadmins to provide up to date performance metrics as hardware configurations change.

ai-ml-benchmark 0.1.2: Comparison across 6 GPU types on M3, CUDA 10.1.105; CuDNN 7.6.5

Figure 2a. Results of benchmarking GPUs on Monash M3.

ai-ml-benchmark 0.1.2 Comparison across 3 GPU types, CUDA 10.1.243; CuDNN 7.6.5

Figure 2b. Results of benchmarking GPUs on UQ Wiener.

- Developed and ran [machine learning workshops and seminars](#) focused on tackling very large datasets using multiple GPUs on HPC infrastructure. Workshops and seminars were run at Monash and the University of Queensland using HPC resources and the Horovod multi-GPU framework. Topics covered included:

- Setup and configuration of multi-GPU machine learning python environment on HPC. Explaining the difference between the environments commonly used on workstations and those required for HPC.
- Job management on HPC queues. How to configure jobs to run on HPC systems using slurm.
- Principles of code parallelisation for multi-GPU use with the Horovod framework. Walkthrough the process of converting serial code to operate in parallel using multiple GPUs. Describe the effects that parallelisation has on machine learning algorithms and the steps required to mitigate them.
- Performance monitoring of jobs. Various tools required to ensure that code is running efficiently were covered. Demonstrated how these tools can be used to check that the environment is configured correctly.
- Course material including sample code developed and made available via a shared repository. The material was structured to be easily adapted to different sites (i.e., Monash and UQ).
- Published this new knowledge and advice through a blog-style [post](#) for the national audience on ML4AU and as usable code repositories at [Monash](#) and [UQ](#) (with examples), and a new training [course](#).
- Improved documentation and effort to ensure users are [checkpointing](#) their models during training to prevent loss of work and unnecessary duplication of compute resources.

WP3: Training in Tools, Libraries, Environments, and Data

This activities of this work package aimed to improve researchers' ML skills and confidence through increased access to training and educational opportunities, including:

- Development of new training material tailored to the research community.
- Delivery of training and upskilling activities via events such as workshops and presentations.
- Creating opportunities for the national research community to access relevant training material and events.

The aim was to upskill researchers in the skills and technical knowledge required to implement modern machine learning techniques while utilising state of the art machine learning software and hardware platforms and environments including those developed in this project.

These outcomes were achieved by:

- Running user and community [surveys](#) across institutions to assess the needs and requirements of our target user group. The surveys heavily influenced the type and style of training material and training events we eventually delivered.
- Development of new training material for the research community. Newly developed material was structured as workshops and lectures that included the following topics:
 - [Getting started with deep learning](#)
 - [Introduction to deep learning and TensorFlow](#)

- [Deep learning for natural language processing](#)
- [Semi-supervised deep learning](#)
- [Introduction to machine learning for imaging](#)
- [Advanced machine learning image segmentation with UNET](#)
- [Data visualisation and storytelling](#)
- [Deep learning for HPC](#)
- Training material was developed in a collaborative fashion with partners within this project and also with external partners such as Pawsey and NCI.
- All developed training material was made publicly available in an open source repository with a creative commons licence.
- Training material was advertised publicly on the national training registry [DReSA](#) and [ML4AU](#).
- Many workshops and lectures were hosted by project partners throughout the duration of the project. All workshops had at least some seats made available to participants outside of the hosting organisation. Some workshops were entirely nationally oriented; that is, all seats were made available to participants around Australia.
- [Train-the-trainer sessions](#) were conducted to upskill teaching assistants who were interested to teach in these workshops.
- Project partners conducted TA-exchanges where teaching assistants from one institution were sent to help out in workshops hosted by another partner institution. This allowed knowledge transfer at the teacher level and also allowed each partner to observe and learn best practices in teaching from another institution.
- A [national training map](#) consisting of a map of relevant machine learning skills, and a map of nationally available training resources was created to facilitate the bigger picture view of the state of training in Australia.

WP4: Communities of Practice and Outreach

A key aim of Work Package 4 was to establish communities of practice around ML in an academic research context and to put measures in place to ensure that the benefits of this ARDC project are sustained beyond the lifetime of this project. The [ML4AU.community](#) website is an important part of this strategy and represents a national platform for the ML community to share and discover opportunities.

Key user groups include:

- Researchers who apply or intend to apply ML to their research, irrespective of their expertise levels or field of work;
- Practitioner communities, who have hands on expertise in ML and can assist others;
- Training groups and volunteers interested in ML curriculum development and delivery;
- Infrastructure (e.g. HPC) providers who host specialist infrastructure for ML.

ML4AU Community of Practice [launched](#) nationally on the 15th of April 2021 and provided a collaborative opportunity for anyone interested in ML for research. The launch witnessed 78+

participants from 14 organisations exchange their experiences and common challenges. Deliverables and activities included:

- A public-facing website to showcase the new ML capabilities and events at MASSIVE (Monash), Wiener (UQ), and affiliated advanced computing centres.
 - [Meetings webpage](#)
 - [Events webpage](#)
 - [Trainings webpage](#)
- Website page(s) to provide resources for researchers interested in ML, including links to internal and external training opportunities, example scripts and code for typical ML workflows and frameworks
 - [Content for Trainers](#)
 - [Tools](#)
 - [Data Collections](#)
- Community meetings to discuss the challenges across trainings, skills and application of ML on HPC
 - [Meeting reports](#)
 - [Meeting recordings](#)
- National ML Showcase events to identify common opportunities, skill gaps, and challenges. The aim was to build a collaborative community through ML4AU. Three showcase events were facilitated to publicise successful applications of ML to research with speakers presenting their projects on the three priority themes:
 - Imaging
 - System Monitoring and Forecasting
 - Natural Language Processing
 - [Showcase event reports](#)
 - [Event recordings](#)
 - These events were successful with 200+ participants and were well received by the ML community
- A “Birds of a Feather” (BoF) [workshop](#) at eResearch Australasia conference, 11th of October, 2021, partnership with Jingbo Wang from NCI. The BoF showcased the ML4AU community and activities.
- A second BoF [workshop](#) focused more toward HPC administrators and users on the challenges of supporting the needs of ML researchers, also on 11th of October 2021..
- [Github repository](#) to collate ML example scripts, tailor made for HPC systems at each partner location
- A key action from Community Meeting #2 was for the community to develop a portal to aggregate details and expertise of qualified trainers across Australia to support national sharing of talent. [This was implemented successfully](#) and integrated into the existing website.
- Creation of a mailing list with close to 260 members who subscribed for updates from ML4AU
- Established a [slack workspace](#) for the community as a platform to interact with other members in the ML/AI research space
- Established communities of practice around identified domains like NLP, imaging etc. (Monash)

- [NLP community slack channel](#)
- [HPC admins for ML](#)
- ML4AU has an organising committee with representatives across various organisations like Monash, University of Queensland, QCIF, NCI, Pawsey, Intersect and ARDC. ARDC has nominated an AI/ML research data specialist to support the organising committee to keep the community active after the duration of the Platform project.

Case Studies

Case-studies are an important part of Work Package 4. We have completed two case studies of researchers who have benefited from the output of this ARDC project and achieved considerable research impact, and two case studies where we aimed to understand the needs of researchers in emerging applications of machine learning. These case studies have been shared nationally through ARDC newsletters and showcase presentations.

[Case Study #1](#) represents a successful example of our strategy to provide training, expert support, and an active community for researchers interested in ML to accelerate discovery. The idea is that even a small advance in knowledge of ML and its potential is enough to spark a ground-breaking idea, a new collaboration, and a major step forward for a field of work. In this case, a PhD student at UQ's Institute for Molecular Bioscience participated in our Deep Learning training course and then converted that knowledge into a successful research proposal for [HealthHack](#). HealthHack is a community event led by Dr. Nick Hamilton (team leader on this ARDC project) in which ML and tech experts come together to solve a curated set of challenges. Machine learning was used to automate a labour-intensive step in electron microscopy image processing, saving weeks of researcher time and generating high-quality models of single molecules for drug discovery programs. This work, and the role of this ARDC-funded project in facilitating it, has been featured on several institutional sites including:

- an [article](#) on the ARDC "News" page related to our [ML4AU](#) community site.
- an [article](#) on UQ's Research and Computing Centre page.

[Case Study #2](#) demonstrates the value of direct collaboration between researchers and the machine-learning experts within our advanced computing centres (e.g. RCC and IMB at UQ, DSAI platform at Monash), and in making use of the powerful compute infrastructure. The research involves imaging of living cells using 'lattice lightsheet microscopes' - a relatively new breed of instrument capable of generating huge amounts of volumetric, time series data. The amount of data makes it difficult for researchers to thoroughly survey and curate these datasets. To cope with the volume of data, and help researchers identify pertinent cellular activity, Oliver Cairncross (a team member of this project) and the RCC developed an application (*Phoebe*) to automatically manage, process, and view the data. To solve the "needle in a haystack" problem, Dr James G. Lefevre (IMB) implemented a machine learning model to detect specific types of cellular behaviour. This machine learning model has been

integrated into Phoebe and supports ground-breaking research that would otherwise be intractable. This case study has been documented [here](#).

[Case Study #3](#) Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) is a powerful non-invasive imaging technique for diagnosis as well as understanding structure and function of the brain and the body. MRI has been revolutionised by several new high-resolution imaging technologies in recent years. However, the large amounts of data lead to slow processing times and in many cases manual annotation of the imaging data is both common and very time consuming.

Our third case study describes a series of projects that broadly aim to use machine learning to be able to speed up MRI image reconstruction, reduce scan time and automatically identify, quantify and annotate images with the goal to be able to bring the latest advances in MRI into clinical and neuroscience applications to make MRI more affordable outside of specialist imaging centres and increase patient throughput, diagnostic accuracy and patient comfort.

Overall machine learning research in MRI is pushing the limits of current computational hardware, storage, software, and visualisation resources and methods. As such, it is an ideal field to discover innovation in solving these problems that might be applied to other fields. This case study has been written up as a formal [report](#) and as a lay-person [story](#) for institutional newsletters and websites, including the ARDC distribution.

[Case Study #4](#) HPC systems consume significant amounts of power – the world’s largest systems can use as much as a small town. As software compiler technologies for High Performance Computing (HPC) become increasingly complex, environmental considerations grow in importance, and the user base expands into many fields that have not previously used HPC, the need to be able to automatically optimise compute energy usage and understand the trade-off with performance only increases.

In this case study, multi-objective machine learning models were developed to identify and predict performance and energy trade-offs on HPC systems. The project successfully demonstrated that significant trade-offs can be identified from parameters that application users can directly control, thereby giving researchers the potential to make low cost and practical informed choices about energy usage and performance when utilising HPC systems.

More broadly, in the energy sector nationally, machine learning techniques are emerging as a critical technology towards optimising usage, reducing waste and minimising costs.

4. Achievements against project work packages:

Record achievement of project work packages, including details of the deliverables, in the table below or in a spreadsheet if preferred.

Use the following criteria and colours to assign a status to each work package:

Status Key

Non-completion has no impact on outcome	Not yet completed, however, has no impact on project outcomes. Responsibility for completion has been assigned and agreed by the Steering Committee.
Non-completion has some impact on project outcomes	Not yet completed and non-completion may have some impact on the project outcomes. Delay has been accepted by the Steering Committee and responsibility for completion has been assigned.
Will not be completed and has impact on project outcomes	Will not be completed and has an impact on the project outcomes. The Steering Committee has accepted the non-completion and understands the impact to the project outcomes.
Completed	Completed.

Please find the itemised deliverables in this [spreadsheet](#). An alternative version [here](#) contains more details, including links to all artefacts.

5. Issues/Challenges

Please list **significant** issues or challenges encountered during project delivery, using the following table or [link to an Issues register](#).

#	Date Opened	Description of Issue	Status Update / Description of resolution	Status	Date closed	Issue Owner
	<i>Date issue was opened</i>	<i>Provide a brief description of the issue</i>	<i>Provide an update of the status of the issue and/or note how the issue was resolved</i>	<i>Open Closed</i>	<i>Date issue was closed</i>	<i>Who is responsible for this issue?</i>
	07/05/21	Departure of Lance Wilson (senior DevOps)	Responsibilities transferred to Chris Hines and Kiowa Scott-hurley	Closed	07/06/21	Wojtek Goscinski

	01/06/21	Departure of Wojtek Goscinski (Project Lead)	Responsibilities transferred to Lead Padmanabhan	Closed	01/06/217	Komathy Padmanabhan and Paul Bonnington
	11/01/22	Departure of CI Komathy Padmanabhan (Project Lead)	Responsibilities transferred to Paul Bonnington	Closed	11/02/22	Komathy Padmanabhan / Paul Bonnington and Paul Bonnington
	01/07/21	Delays in hardware procurement meant that some services will not be usable by a national audience until beyond the life of this project	Sustainability plan includes details of national GPU use and MLeRP environment, including a plan for implementation and oversight	Open	-	Paul Bonnington, in consultation with Paul Coddington and other ARDC representative S.

6. Project Acceptance

Have all the original needs of the stakeholders been met, and are there any ongoing concerns that need to be documented and/or addressed?

All milestones have been achieved and documented. One in-progress activity is the sustainability of one aspect of the work in WP1 (the national ML notebook environment platform). The future state of this work is under discussion with the ARDC and will be subject to separate reporting requirements.

7. Sustainability plans

Please indicate what plans have been put in place for continued operation of the platform, and how these will be supported.

Monash University and the University of Queensland have strong track records of sustaining the benefits of nationally funded work. The sustainability of the deliverables under this project is ensured through several key mechanisms:

1. Many of the deliverables involve the establishment of Communities of Practice, which will require only modest oversight or maintenance to endure. The communities we have established will continue to e.g. events, training, example scripts, tools, data collections etc, supported by the eResearch teams and partners institutions.
 - a. ML4AU CoP: The national ML Community of Practice will remain active and vibrant beyond the tenure of this funding. As described throughout this report, we have established a large group of motivated researchers and formalised the community through e-mail/contact distributions, Slack Channels, and shared community resources (e.g. website for sharing training opportunities or qualified tutors). We have consulted widely within our teams, partners, and with the ARDC (particularly Gnana Bharathy) and agreed to establish a national committee to oversee the CoP and coordinate future activities and initiatives. Gnana has confirmed his ability to devote time to this role in 2022 and the committee membership will be established from our existing pool of national contacts and governance participants (e.g. Steering/Advisory committee members).
 - b. Monash's community of MASSIVE-M3 users interested in ML: We have been running biannual community meetings with Monash researchers to showcase the latest resources and compute available on MASSIVE. These meetings have been popular and will continue in 2022 and beyond.
 - c. [NLP community slack channel](#)
 - d. [HPC admins for ML](#)
2. Alignment of project deliverables with priority areas for participating institutions and national initiatives.
 - a. ML environments: Strudel2 is now well established and in regular use by many researchers. It is popular, effective, and will be supported operationally under existing resources and arrangements at Monash. This includes alignment with another funded ARDC project ("The Australian Characterisation Commons at Scale"; ACCS).
 - b. MLeRP: The MLeRP GPU-enabled notebook platform builds directly on the success of Strudel2 and inherits much of the support from its conceptual parent. The national delivery of MLeRP is an ongoing discussion between Monash, QCIF, UQ, and ARDC (particularly with Paul Coddington) and will be aligned with the ARDC National GPU Service. This aspect of the work has been identified as a separate enduring collaboration with the ARDC and will be planned and reported separately in future submissions to the ARDC.
3. Living documents and repositories
 - a. Code repositories, training materials, and example scripts: the resources provided for ML researchers are live, public repositories (shared via ML4AU) and will be maintained through an active community, as tools and libraries evolve. Over the longer term, new repositories would need to be created if and when there is a fundamental change to the "tools of the trade" (as there was when deep-learning, tensorflow, and pytorch

revolutionised the ML space). If the community cannot provide this level of input, new funding will be sought.

- b. The benchmarking tools are public and readily re-usable as hardware configurations change over the coming years. This should provide a low cost and low barrier to maintaining their relevance in the medium term. Different tools and measurements might be required in the longer term, which would require investment from the partner institutions or external sources (e.g. ARDC).
- c. Documentation: partner institutions invest in ongoing maintenance of documentation. There is little or no additional cost to maintain the ML-aspects of this work.

Lessons learnt

8. What went well?

What positive lessons can be usefully applied to other projects? Did the ARDC support/partnership benefit the project's outcomes?

Example:

- *CoP sessions were scheduled at the right time of year and held as a hybrid delivery. When scheduling we considered the academic calendar and other competing events such as conferences. Providing the ability to meet F2F and via zoom ensured that there was good collaboration regardless of the location of the CoP member.*
- Having flexibility built into work packages enabled us to engage directly with researchers to find out more about their needs. For example, after delivering Jupyter Notebooks as part of Strudel 2 for WP 1.1.3, we received feedback that a large portion of the community wanted remote access to the HPC via Visual Studio Code. We were able to pivot and implement this due to work package flexibility.
- Some of the more experimental work packages had less impact than expected, such as WP.1.2.3 for hosting central data collections. We discovered later on in the project that in order for researchers to utilise central datasets, we either had to contact them directly after finding they had multiple dataset copies, or wait for them to ask for more personal storage to highlight we were able to manage some data for them.
- Running community meetings at Monash was a fantastic opportunity to showcase our work and gather feedback from the community. The meetings also gave us insight into our research impact, encouraging us to continue delivering at the highest possible quality.
- The two year project timeline made it difficult to review previously completed work packages and improve on them; for example, we discovered recently developed benchmarks late into the

project that would have given us additional data on the best way to use infrastructure for machine learning, but had limited time to test additional benchmarks.

- Collaborating across national institutions ensured what we delivered was aligned with national interests, and not confined in usefulness to our local sites. This means much of the work is reusable.
- Collaborating on training activities at the national level allowed us to service the national community that would otherwise have been improbable. It allowed the larger group to focus on the bigger picture, create opportunities for those who would have otherwise been left out, and exchange expertise across institutions.
- The project fostered many good relationships between organisations and also at the individual level that hopefully would lead to a closer knit community and future collaborations.
- Funding from the project directly contributed to the running of many training activities, benefiting hundreds of community members across the country. This would not have been possible had the various organisations not been brought together under one umbrella.
- The ML4AU Community of Practice has made a considerable impact and will continue beyond the life of this project.

9. What could be improved?

Are there lessons learnt that can usefully be applied to other projects? i.e.

- Were risks identified early enough and were mitigation strategies effective?
- Were there any issues that could have been avoided? If so, how?
- Could any issues/risks be avoided for future projects?
- Were there any changes to the project as originally planned? If so, are there any reflections or considerations which could be considered for future similar projects?
- How can ARDC’s support/partnership improve to meet the project’s needs?

Description	Impact on project	What was actioned/could be a solution(s) for future projects
<p><i>This is an example only:</i></p> <p><i>The project governance structures were not effective</i></p>	<p><i>This is an example only:</i></p> <p><i>The reporting lines between the technical committee and the steering committee were not clear, and there was no process for making technical decisions/forming consensus between project partners. This</i></p>	<p><i>This is an example only:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Develop Terms of Reference for all project governance groups, which include decision making processes, and reporting lines.</i> ● <i>Project plan must include roles and associated responsibilities that are agreed upon by all</i>

	<i>led to delays in agreeing on the technical architecture, with consequent delays in delivery.</i>	<i>partners</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>One person (the project manager or a technical lead) needs explicit authority to drive the work packages of all partner organisations, with all orgs/WPs accountable to that person and ultimately the SC.</i>
Planning and execution of activities, especially those directly involving community participation, was largely top-down from the project leadership (though informed by community surveys).	A top-down approach for the duration of the project meant there was no organic leadership committee or team to take over the role once this project ends.	At the same time as building a CoP, more effort could be put into building the future leadership team. This happened to an extent through our national ML Community Meetings (informing choices about all activities), but we did not formally establish a committee of those members.
ML4AU events were each centred on a very broad topic and across many research domains	A broad focus allowed us to draw in a wide audience and form a CoP, but also made it harder for individuals to form organic partnerships around more fine-grained topics or techniques. We expect greater participation and collaboration will arise from future events that drill down into more focused areas.	A more balanced combination of large-broad and small-focused events. This would get the best of both worlds: a broad, connected community of ML users, and direct benefit to individuals that would better motivate them to engage and contribute within their domain. This also improves the sustainability of the CoPs.
The project successfully proved that training activities are popular, but development of new material beyond the life of this project is unfunded and cannot be guaranteed.	There is no direct impact on the execution of the project, but it diminishes the long term value of the communities and inertia generated.	More effort to ensure there is a plan for long term financial support.
The collection of metrics was a challenge and could be done better in future. Metrics were not sufficiently clearly defined up front, in part because the deliverables matured over time and the required metrics became clearer over time.	The reported metrics are a good representation of the work and impact, but there is some ambiguity about whether definitions were consistent across reporting milestones.	More awareness of this challenge, more effort to ensure that deliverables are as clear as possible before commencing the project, and more firm effort to ensure that collection of relevant performance data is built into the operational work of the team.

<p>The data collection mechanism (spreadsheets) could have been clearer and more well-suited to the collection of incremental metrics with each reporting period.</p> <p>These effects interacted with the issue of staff turnover. For example, to collect user information for ML environments, sys admins would use custom scripts or commands to extract key pieces of information (e.g. number of users of a service. These methods were somewhat opaque to the broader team and not sufficiently transferred to new staff.</p>		
<p>Timing of hardware procurement</p>	<p>Delayed implementation of a national ML environment.</p>	<p>This was largely driven by impacts of COVID19 and might not have relevance for future projects.</p>

10. Anything else you would like to tell us about the project:

FAIR

11. FAIR Project Outputs

Describe how the **project** outputs (publications, documentation, code, etc) have been made FAIR, with particular focus on any reuse or potential for reuse of outputs beyond the original purpose.

- The [ML4AU.community](https://ml4au.com) website - a national, open-access resource for identifying training opportunities, compute resources, example scripts, and support

- Code to benchmark the GPUs on M3 is available on GitHub:
<https://github.com/kiowa-scott-hurley/ARDC-ML/tree/main/ai-benchmark>
- Code to monitor job resource usage on M3 is available on Github:
<https://github.com/kiowa-scott-hurley/ARDC-ML/tree/main/job-monitoring>
- Code to checkpoint code is available on docs.massive:
<https://docs.massive.org.au/communities/machine-learning.html>
- AI with Deep Learning, including code to convert notebooks to Python files, is available via Github: (we intend to add this to the other github eventually as a stand-alone resource):
<https://github.com/mitchellshargreaves/AI-With-Deep-Learning>
- Instructions to download data collections on M3 in the ml_data_collections branch (pending a merge request) is available via Github:
https://github.com/Characterisation-Virtual-Laboratory/Data_Collections/tree/ml_data_collections_docs
- Introduction to Deep Learning and Tensorflow - Training presentation and notebooks (245 views and 39 downloads as of March 2021) <https://doi.org/10.26180/13100519>
- Deep Learning for Natural Language Processing - Training presentation and notebooks (320 views and 30 downloads and 2 tweets) <https://doi.org/10.26180/13100513>
- Visualisation and Storytelling - Training presentation and notebooks (180 views and 23 downloads) <https://doi.org/10.26180/13100510>
- Semi Supervised Deep Learning - training presentation and notebooks
<https://doi.org/10.26180/14176805>
- Introduction to Network Visualisation - Training presentation and datasets
<https://github.com/doktor-nick/intro-to-network-viz>
- Introduction to Machine Learning for Imaging - Training presentation and datasets
<https://github.com/doktor-nick/intro-to-ml-for-imaging>
- Advanced machine learning image segmentation with UNET - Training presentation and datasets
<https://github.com/doktor-nick/adv-ML-image-segmentation-with-UNET>
- Deep learning for HPC
<https://github.com/ML4AU/Horovod-on-HPC>

12. Implementing FAIR Platforms

Describe how the Platform itself is FAIR, with particular focus on any reuse or potential for reuse of platform components beyond the original purpose (if this is not already described in Section 11).

Not applicable as this project does not have a software Platform associated.

13. Implementing FAIR-enabling Platforms

Describe what functions/features have been implemented in the Platform to enable FAIR outputs (i.e. how are data, code, visualisations, etc produced or processed by the Platform made FAIR/FAIRer).

Not applicable as this project does not have a software Platform associated.

Project Impact

The Government wishes to demonstrate the impact on researchers (and industry and the general public) of the NCRIS investment, and the ARDC Board is particularly concerned with being able to demonstrate the value of the investment in Research Platforms.

ARDC realises that a number of possible impact metrics are lag indicators.

14. Platform impact metrics

Executive summary

	Total
Infrastructure (WP1 and WP2)	
Primary*	173
Secondary*	1145
Training and Community (WP3 and WP4)	
Training attendees	1931
Training events	47

Community events	93
Community event attendees	2109

* **Primary unique** users are defined as those who explicitly register for and/or use the new tools and infrastructure developed under WPs 1 and 2. They are identifiable and trackable. **Secondary unique** users are those who have access to the new resources and in most cases (e.g. those who access new data collections) are not readily identifiable or trackable. The number provided in that case is the total number of identified machine learning users on Monash’s MASSIVE and UQ’s Weiner infrastructure.

For Work Package 1, the focus of the metrics reported here is on usage of our newly developed HPC-based environments for data science and machine learning. Users of these environments count toward the **primary** metrics in the table above and are detailed in Table 1 and Figure 3 below. Environments include simple web-access interfaces for Jupyter Lab and notebooks, with all computation running on Monash’s M3 cluster and with standard or custom Python/Conda environments/kernels (“BYO”). These environments make it easy to quickly prototype an ML application or analysis and also provide a platform to support large-scale training and outreach activities in WP 3 and WP 4. The spike in usage in December 2020 (seen in Table 1 and Figure 3) reflects the first successful use of the JupyterLab platform for ML training.

For Work Package 2, the focus of the metrics reported here is (i) the usage of the three newly hosted reference data collections for machine learning (e.g. the classic “ImageNet” collection of images). Hosting popular and large reference data sets makes them readily available to users without delay or difficulty and prevents costly duplications in the file system that otherwise occurs with individual user access; (ii) Improved documentation and example scripts to enhance ML performance and support ML at scale. This includes advice on checkpointing to prevent unnecessary duplication of work and the results of our benchmarking analyses of GPU resources to assist users to identify the right choice for the ML task at hand. These metrics are not easily tracked and count toward the **secondary** users in the table above.

For Work Packages 3 and 4, we have captured a large number of variables, reported and described below in Table 2. They summarise community engagement with the new training material we have developed (as well as existing material), locally within institutions and nationally through the broader roll-out of our activities. It also includes engagement with our new ML4AU.community website, intended as the nation’s go-to site for ML training, events, and resources for researchers. Further details of the site are provided below as an Impact Story. Data on engagement with the site is provided in Figure 4 below.

WP1: Accessible Tools, Libraries, Environments, and Data							
WP2: Machine Learning at Scale							
	Primary users	M4/M5	detailed below				
	Secondary users*	M4	835				
		M5	1145				
		Final report	1145				
* Secondary users are unidentifiable and include users from other national institutions							
Report	Active Users						
	Time	Jupyter Lab	Jupyter Lab BYO	Data Collections	Total		
M4	August 2020	4	0	19	23		
	September 2020	2	0	0	2		
	October 2020	2	0	0	2		
	November 2020	2	1	0	3		
	December 2020	22	3	0	25		
	January 2021	5	4	2	11		
	February 2021	1	1	9	11		
M5	March 2021	10	5	5	20		
	April 2021	5	6	1	12		
	May 2021	14	6	0	20		
	June 2021	12	5	2	19		
	July 2021	19	3	6	28		
	August 2021	14	11	5	30		
	September 2021	10	8	1	19		
Final report	October 2021	21	6	6	33		
	November 2021	10	4	5	19		
	December 2021	10	10	3	23		
	January 2022	17	25	7	49		
	February 2022	17	15	17	49		
Report	Registrations				Cumulative		
	Time	Jupyter Lab	Jupyter Lab BYO	Total	Jupyter Lab	Jupyter Lab BYO	Total
M4	August 2020	4	0	4	4	0	4
	September 2020	1	0	1	5	0	5
	October 2020	1	0	1	6	0	6
	November 2020	2	1	3	8	1	9
	December 2020	21	2	23	29	3	32
	January 2021	1	2	3	30	5	35
	February 2021	5	4	9	35	9	44
M5	March 2021	5	1	6	40	10	50
	April 2021	3	5	8	43	15	58
	May 2021	7	4	11	50	19	69
	June 2021	4	2	6	54	21	75
	July 2021	7	3	10	61	24	85
	August 2021	8	7	15	69	31	100
	September 2021	5	3	8	74	34	108
	October 2021	10	3	13	84	37	121
	November 2021	1	1	2	85	38	123
	December 2021	5	8	13	90	46	136
	January 2022	10	19	29	100	65	165
	February 2022	4	4	8	104	69	173

Table 1. The number of active users and new registrations. Note that the JupyterLab environments are currently in beta-testing and have not yet been widely advertised to the community.

Figure 3. Active users as in Table 1 and new registrations plotted cumulatively, both plotted as stacked histograms.

WP3: Training in Tools, Libraries, Environments, and Data					
WP4: Communities of Practice and Outreach					
				Total	
Training	Training events			47	
	Researchers trained (online or face-to-face)*			1931	
	Institutions represented in trainings			78	
	New trainings developed			8	
	Train the trainer sessions			3	
	Open source trainings developed			8	
	Training materials were downloaded			564	
	Training materials shared on social media and other platforms			0	
	Training collaborations across organisations			22	
	Industry trainings			1	
Community	Total community events			93	
	Total community event attendees			2109	
	Hacky Hour Community events (UQ)	Meetings			86
		Attendees			1072
	ML Community Meetings (Monash)	Meetings			4
		Attendees			188
	Social media mentions of platform*			21	
	Website visits			3679	
	Unique website visits			2500	
	Institutions represented in community activities			10	
	ML4AU mailing list members			257	
	ML4AU Showcase events	Events			3
		Attendees			231

Outcomes	New ML research projects that originated from training and engagements?			3
	Career-stage metrics			
		Undergrad		11
		Postgrad		262
		ECR		102
		Senior academic		50
		Other staff		9
	Researchers trained by state			0
		New South Wales		79
		Queensland		514
		South Australia		9
		Tasmania		4
		Victoria		1127
		Western Australia		29
		Northern Territory		0
		Australian Capital Territory		17
				43
	Regional training			121
	Training feedback			128

Table 2. Metrics for Work Packages 3 and 4.

Figure 4. A snapshot of traffic to the ML4AU website.

Top Sources by Visits [VIEW SOURCES](#)

Top Devices by Visits

15. Links to publications and other communications

Published datasets generated by platform

N/A

Publications using data generated by platform

N/A

Publications that cite/reference the platform

N/A

Social media mentions of the platform

Date	Link
<i>Example:</i> July 2020	https://twitter.com/AusBiocommons/status/1251724453173538817?s=20
April 2021	https://twitter.com/ARDC_AU/status/1382888395618271234?s=20
April 2021	https://twitter.com/ARDC_AU/status/1379207372879581184?s=20&t=-WVAN4se4vEbv7HcnTHQ
April 2021	https://twitter.com/ARDC_AU/status/1381426929807548423?s=20&t=-WVAN4se4vEbv7HcnTHQ

	vt7HcnTHQ
May 2021	https://twitter.com/PawseyCentre/status/1389754230135738372?s=20&t=-WVAN4se4vEbv7HcnTHQ
May 2021	https://twitter.com/ARDC_AU/status/1391634133466636290?s=20&t=-WVAN4se4vEbv7HcnTHQ
May 2021	https://twitter.com/ARDC_AU/status/1394549576355418114?s=20&t=-WVAN4se4vEbv7HcnTHQ
July 2021	https://twitter.com/ARDC_AU/status/1412894345309528067?s=20&t=-WVAN4se4vEbv7HcnTHQ
July 2021	https://twitter.com/MonasheResearch/status/1417642829250056193?s=20&t=-WVAN4se4vEbv7HcnTHQ
July 2021	https://twitter.com/AusBiocommons/status/1418422452200218631?s=20&t=-WVAN4se4vEbv7HcnTHQ
August 2021	https://twitter.com/CDataCommons/status/1422399530360737802?s=20&t=-WVAN4se4vEbv7HcnTHQ
August 2021	https://twitter.com/sbollmann_MRI/status/1423072916845985795?s=20&t=-WVAN4se4vEbv7HcnTHQ
August 2021	https://twitter.com/ARDC_AU/status/1425592988525334529?s=20&t=-WVAN4se4vEbv7HcnTHQ
October 2021	https://twitter.com/ARDC_AU/status/1447306022297669642?s=20&t=-WVAN4se4vEbv7HcnTHQ
October 2021	https://twitter.com/IntersectAust/status/1447360827196014597?s=20&t=-WVAN4se4vEbv7HcnTHQ
November 2021	https://twitter.com/NCInews/status/1461211855288864771?s=20&t=-WVAN4se4vEbv7HcnTHQ

Blog posts/news articles that reference the platform

Date	Link
<i>Example:</i> July 2020	https://twitter.com/AusBiocommons/status/1251724453173538817?s=20
March 2021	https://ardc.edu.au/news/launching-ml4au-a-machine-learning-community-of-practice-for-australia/

April 2021	https://mailchi.mp/ardc.edu.au/nov2020-1892106
May 2021	https://ardc.edu.au/resources/communities-of-practice/
May 2021	https://datascienceweek.org/past-events/
August 2021	https://nci.org.au/news-events/events/ai-and-ml-system-monitoring-and-forecasting-ml4au-showcase-2
January 2022	https://www.nci.org.au/news-events/events/ml4au-community-meeting-0

16. Details on engagement, outreach and training activities

Two Work Packages are devoted to engagement, outreach, and training. These outputs have been described in Section 3. Some additional details are included here.

Training

- Training delivered to date. Reported values are totals within the tenure of this project’s funding.

Training	Internal/national courses	Number of participants	Number of organisations
Introduction to Deep Learning and TensorFlow	7 internal, 4 national	460	17
Deep Learning for NLP	5 internal, 1 national	240	22
Visualisation and Storytelling	4 internal, 1 national	200	17
AI with Deep Learning and PyTorch	1 internal	40	3
Semi Supervised Deep Learning	1 internal, 1 external	75	17
Getting Started with Deep Learning	2 external	355	43

Introduction to Graph Visualisation	2 internal	40	Unavailable
Linear Regression in R	4 internal	154	16
Linear Mixed Models in R	2 internal	135	8
Introduction to Machine Learning for Imaging	8 internal	268	7

- New trainings under development
 - Self Supervised Deep Learning

New course: Semi Supervised Deep Learning

This workshop covers various semi-supervised learning techniques available in the literature. The workshop consists of a lecture introducing at a high level a selection of techniques that are suitable for semi-supervised deep learning. We discuss how these techniques can be implemented and the underlying assumptions they require. The lecture is followed by a hands-on session where attendees implement a semi-supervised learning technique to train a neural network. We observe and discuss the changing performance and behaviour of the network as varying degrees of labelled and unlabelled data is provided to the network during training.

New lecture: Getting Started with Deep Learning

This lecture provides a high level overview of how you could get started with developing deep learning applications. It introduces deep learning in a nutshell and then provides advice relating to the concepts and skill sets you would need to know and have in order to build a deep learning application. The lecture also provides pointers to various resources you could use to gain a stronger foothold in deep learning.

This lecture is targeted at researchers who may be complete beginners in machine learning, deep learning, or even with programming, but who would like to get into the space to build AI systems hands-on.

New course: Advanced Machine Learning Image Segmentation with UNET

A hands-on workshop on using UNET machine learning architectures for image segmentation using the Tensorflow/Keras frameworks. The first third of the workshop covers the principles of image segmentation and UNET. The second two thirds walk attendees through real-world coding examples and datasets. Topics for the workshop include: a brief introduction to Keras; convolutions, skipping and max pooling; the structure of UNET; tiling and batch sizes, memory limitations; data augmentation; image generators; metrics for measuring image/mask similarity; loss functions for images/masks; optimiser choice; using Google Colab for development. Interactive example and code: Electron Microscopy imaging segmentation. The free Google Colab environment is utilised by attendees to run examples.

New course: Deep learning on HPC

A Deep Learning on HPC workshop has been designed for experienced users that require, or would benefit from, using high performance computing resources to carry out their deep learning work. GPU enabled clusters such as UQ's Wiener and Monash's MASSIVE are great platforms to perform deep learning tasks. Workshop participants will gain an understanding on how to utilise the features found on these platforms such as:

- Accelerators for high speed numerical computation (GPU's);
- Fast, high capacity file systems;
- High speed networking; and
- Job queuing systems.

The workshop is based on a case study demonstrating various concepts required to run deep learning code on HPC platforms and ultimately teaches how to reimplement single process code as multi process (parallel GPU) code. Given it isn't feasible to address even a fraction of any real world examples; the workshop is restricted to a single DL framework—Keras; as well as a single use case—image classification. Nevertheless, participants will gain a general understanding of how to write parallel GPU code and deploy it on HPC systems.

The workshop targets participants that already have experience with:

- writing and running Python based deep learning code;
- python environment management; and
- the Linux command line interface.

Although the workshop is tailored to specific HPC clusters it can be adapted to any multi GPU system.

Community engagement

1. University of Queensland is part of the annual [HealthHack](#) event conducted in Queensland that connects medical researchers, healthcare professionals, and people with health related IT problems, with developers, designers and educators, from the university and commercial sectors in order to build solutions. All software created is made [publicly available](#) under open source licenses, and final pitches to the judges are available on [YouTube](#). HealthHack 2020 was held virtually over 2 weekends in July/August and brought together some 70 solvers to work on 7 problems. Two of the problems from UQ were machine learning related: CryoFilter which was about image classification for protein structure determination, which is used in drug design; and the Auslan Community Data Portal which was about creating a public videoset of Auslan for use in machine learning. The former has been written up as a case study for this project. HealthHack 2020 was very successful in both the solutions developed, as well as in creating a community

across the university and commercial sectors which shared and developed skills and expertise in machine learning.

Unfortunately, there was no HealthHack in 2021 (due to COVID19) and perhaps also not in 2022 (due to the retirement of Dr. Nick Hamilton).

2. Run weekly at The University of Queensland, **Hacky Hour** is a community volunteer run drop-in help session for researchers and students who need help with computation and computational resources. Typical questions revolve around high performance computing, machine learning, Python, R, bioinformatics, and research data management. Hacky Hour is enormously popular, and has typically seen around 30 sessions and up to 500 attendees within a typical reporting period of this project (~6 months).

Monash University conducted various community engagement activities through

- Showcase events
- National ML Community of Practice

International collaborations being discussed

- Penn State University
- Elixir ML focus group

Industry Collaboration underway

- NVIDIA

17. Details on users of the platform

If possible, provide a brief breakdown of where these users come from; for example, which institutions the core user groups are from, or how many users from each of the following broad categories: .edu.au, .gov.au, .org.au, .edu (international academic institutions), .com (gmails etc.), other.

The user community for this project is broad, spanning institutional, national, and international researchers, and across academic, industry, and government partners. Our strategy in developing infrastructure, ML environments, training, and outreach activities has been to first focus within the partner institutions (particularly Monash, UQ, and QCIF) during development stages to ensure quality, performance, and immediate benefits to the research community. We then scale up to deliver nationally as part of our participation in national events (e.g. ARDC Skills Summit) and infrastructure (e.g. NCRIS/Nectar) and the future national ML notebook environments being developed by the platform. Most users are from the project institutions (Monash and QCIF/UQ, ~70%) and national participants have not been formally measured (e.g. training registration required only an e-mail address).

18. Impact stories

Please detail any research impacts or highlights here. Other impacts could include outcomes of industry collaborations, platform community activities leading to new policy or practice, etc. Stories from users of the platform are particularly useful.

This section is primarily covered in Section 3 (see Case Studies, in particular).

The training activities under this project in the form of workshops have enabled researchers to upskill in the areas of AI and machine learning. This has enabled them to initiate research projects in their domain of expertise that leverage on advancements in machine learning. Staff working on this project have been directly involved in further facilitating two such research projects, both in the form of student internships running over multiple months.

1. Dr Jason Crow from Art, Design and Architecture - using generative adversarial networks to develop a creative AI application called "Toolbeing generator". This project is ongoing.
2. Dr Sudha Mani from the Marketing department - using large language models to classify sentences in legal contracts. This project has been completed with success, with the project owners indicating their satisfaction.

Two other research projects are in the planning stages.